

BUILD SMARTER. CLEANER. CHEAPER.

Leading the European construction industry to a low-carbon, climate-resilient digital transformation.

BIMprove harnesses the power of cutting-edge Digital Twin Technology to lead construction sites into the Industry 4.0 revolution.

Our Benefits

www.bimprove-h2020.eu

info@bimprove-h2020.eu

@BIMproveEU

BIMprove H2020 Project

Our Team

Fast-track Operations

Increase scheduling forecast capacity by 20%, automating progress & quality reporting.

- Upgrade BIM models with as-built real-time data
- Productivity step-up with Big Tech: AR/VR, Artificial Intelligence, Drones & Wearables
- Predictive Analysis with early detection of deviations

Downscale Costs

Reduction of costs by 20% in construction projects.

- Cost Planning and Control
- Budget Reliability
- Faster Delivery Date
- Lower Operating Costs

A Green and Safe Construction

Making the industry less exposed to labour accidents and committed to sustainability.

- Continuous Safety Monitoring
- Supply Chain Agility
- Optimized Stockpiling
- Waste Avoidance

BIMprove advocates the European Green Deal

Open and Standard

We follow an Open Innovation approach, building solutions with and for the industry

- x3 Experimentation Use Cases
- Contribution to Standardisation Bodies
- Open Access Repository
- GitHub